

Comparative Study of Spread of COVID-19 following Several Interventions spanning 54 days Reflects a Restricted Movement of SARS-CoV-2 in the Population: A Case for Development of Herd Immunity?

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19 is fast spreading around the globe in a highly contagious manner. In this article we have described the effect of prolonged intervention of 54 days on the growth rate of COVID-19 cases. The results showed that after sporadic volatility in percent of COVID-19 cases, the graph showed stability at $\leq 4.6\%$. The reduced volatility and sustained flattened curve of COVID-19 cases, along with increase in doubling time of rate of COVID-19 cases to 13 days as reported earlier (2), suggested that spread of COVID-19 was gradually slowing down in the population. Concomitant with this, number of discharged/recovered patients from COVID-19 also increased in a steady manner among population. A positive correlation between percent of COVID-19 cases & percent of recovery of patients from COVID-19 existed ($R^2 = 0.246$). Though the correlation between the two variables is weak, increased recovery of patients from COVID-19 with the controlled spread of COVID-19 would plausibly aid in the development of protective immunity in the population.

Key words: COVID-19 – interventions- growth curve- recovery – herd immunity.

I. INTRODUCTION

The novel coronavirus (SARS- COV-2) originated in Wuhan in Hubei province of China during December 2019, and has now spread across the world making it a pandemic. Until date there are no therapeutic agents/vaccines developed which are of promise to control this highly infectious virus from spreading among human population. At this juncture, therefore, controlling the spread of this highly contagious disease is priority. SARS virus belongs to the family *Coronaviridae*, which is known to cause respiratory illnesses in humans and animals. coronavirus (CoV) is a novel member of this family that causes acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), which is associated with high mortality rate. Its characteristic feature is long latency period before a typical flu-like fever, cough, and shortness of breath manifests. The people infected with this virus may not show any early symptoms allowing them to pass it on to others.

Due to alarming nature of this disaster world-wide and to contain its spread at an early stage, a short curfew followed by 'National Lockdown-I' for 21 days starting from 23rd March, 2020 Midnight until Midnight of 14 April, 2020 was implemented by Indian Authorities. We have described earlier a method to monitor the spread of COVID-19 and showed that during this period of Lockdown-I, number of COVID-19 cases abruptly came down, showing a flattened curve until 31 March, 2020 following which there was some volatility due to spurt in the number of cases on 1st April, 2020 onwards (1, 2). At this stage, Lockdown was further extended for two weeks

from 14th April until 30 April, 2020 (Lockdown-II). Following which Lockdown was further extended until 17 May 2020 (Lockdown-III).

In our earlier studies we established that (a) much of the success of Lockdown was reflected in the percent graph (b) the unprecedented changes that took place during Lockdown-I was clearly detectable in the plotted percent graph (c) increase in doubling time of COVID-19 cases had a weak negative correlation with the rate of COVID-19 cases and (d) the percent graph elucidated that long term down-trend of COVID-19 cases remained intact in spite of the volatility in the population(1, 2, 3). In this paper, we have endeavoured to further elucidate the role Lockdown-III and cumulative effect of three Lockdowns, if any on spread of COVID-19 and possible significance of changes on development of Herd immunity.

II. METHOD AND RESULTS: The present study was carried out on the data collected from Indian which were confirmed as COVID-19 positive cases, starting from March 15, 2020 until May 17, 2020, from Government of India and other national News agencies as described previously (1,2).

The **Figure 1** reflects the total number of positive cases of COVID-19/day until 16 May, 2020. The graph reflected that there was a gradual increase in the number of COVID-19 cases since 15 March, 2020 until 17 May, 2020.

The **Figure-2** shows the percent change in COVID-19 cases between 15 March, 2020 and 16 May, 2020. It is clear from **Figure-2** that after Lockdown-I was implemented on 25th March, there was marked decrease in percent of COVID-19 cases in the population, which was stably maintained until 31 March 2020. However, on the 1st of April, 2020 there was 2.5 folds

increase in COVID-19 cases compared to 31 March, 2020. This abrupt change in number of COVID-19 cases appeared as small 'peaks' on the graph as shown in Figure-2. This volatility in percent increase in COVID-19 cases gradually subsided and by 26 April, 2020 it came down to around 5%; the growth curve further flattened and maintained stability at the level of $\leq 4.5\%$ until 16 May, 2020. A comparative study of the percent growth during the three Lockdowns is illustrated in **Figure-3**. The figure shows that during Lockdown-I, there was substantial volatility after 31 March, 2020. This volatility was mainly attributed to abrupt increase in COVID-19 cases from 1st April, 2020 to 6th April, 2020. Following this volatility, the percent graph maintained a stable nature at the level of $\sim 10\%$ until end of Lockdown-I. During Lockdown-II, though there was a general downward trend in the graph, volatility was noted until 26th April, 2020; thereafter the graph stabilised at around $\leq 4.6\%$. During Lockdown-III, however, the growth curve illustrated a less volatile and more stable nature with growth rate of COVID-19 at $\sim 4.5\%$. A significant feature reflected in the graph that from 11th May onwards the graph maintained a flattened nature. The trend line of percent differences of COVID-19 cases during three lockdowns also demonstrated that volatility improved during Lockdown-II & Lockdown-III as compared to Lockdown-I as shown in **Figure-4** ($R^2 = 0.404$ Vs 0.488). With the apparent stability achieved in the percentage graph, the number of patients recovering from COVID-19 also increased during subsequent Lockdowns. While the number of recovered patients from COVID-19 on 29th April, 2020 (Lockdown-II) was 24% with 7797 recovered patients (2), during

Lockdown-III, the percentage of Recovery was 42% on 16th May 2020 as shown in **Figure-5**. When the percent of recovered patients was plotted against the percent change in COVID-19 cases from 8 May to 17 May 2020, it revealed that a weak positive correlation existed between the two variables (**Figure-6**). The trend line suggests that there would be a gradual increase in the number of Recovered/disease free individuals with time (The $R^2 = 0.246$). Taken these finding with our earlier observation that doubling time of COVID-19 cases steadily increased from 3 days to 10 days following implementation of two Lockdowns (2), implies that the Indian population could be steadily moving towards developing protective immunity/herd immunity against COVID-19. The importance of introducing Lockdown & social distancing at the appropriate time is best depicted in **Figure-7** taken from New York Times for population in the USA. The graph shows that by delaying the time of implementing an intervention in the USA, the mortality from COVID-19 substantially increased. Whereas imposing Lockdown-I at an early stage in March 2020 paid dividend for Indian population; the mortality rate has been maintained below ~3%.

III. DISCUSSION:

The disaster caused all over the world by the COVID-19 pandemic has prompted a massive global effort to control spread of the disease in their respective population. At present due to lack of any specific treatment for COVID-19, the importance of implementing Lockdown/social distancing cannot be ignored at all. Delaying implementation of intervention even by

few weeks can cost a country heavily in terms of human lives as depicted in the model shown in Figure-7.

India however, by introducing physical intervention with social distancing rather early on March 23, 2020, when number of COVID-19 positive cases was negligible achieved abrupt arrest of COVID-19 cases and slowed down spread of the contagious SARS-CoV-2 among Indian population (1). Though there was some volatility in the percent increase of COVID-19 cases during Lockdown-I, the volatility gradually subsided during Lockdown-II and Lockdown-III respectively compared to Lockdown-1. The growth rate of COVID-19 stabilised around ~4.5% and a flattened growth curve was maintained until 17th May, 2020, that is 54 days after implementation of Lockdown. This alteration in volatility during progression of successive Lockdowns was reflected from the R^2 value which improved in Lockdown-II and Lockdown-III respectively compared to Lockdown-I (Figure 4). The reduced volatility and sustained flattened curve of COVID-19, along with increase in doubling time in the rate of COVID-19 to 13 days as reported previously (2), suggests that spread of Coronavirus was gradually slowing down in the population (attenuation of SARS-CoV-2 in the population?). Perhaps gradual increase in number of discharged/recovered patients from COVID-19 also points to that direction. Interestingly, a positive correlation between the percent of COVID-19 cases & the percent of recovery of patients from COVID-19 was observed with $R^2 = 0.246$. Though this correlation between the two variables is weak, increased recovery of patients from

COVID-19 with controlled spread of COVID-19 would plausibly aid in development of protective immunity in the population.

A case of protective Immunity: Protective immunity/Herd immunity, also called herd protection, is the resistance to the spread of a contagious disease within a population that results if a sufficiently high proportion of individuals become immune to the disease. It basically serves as an indirect protection to those who are not immune to the disease. This could be achieved either through vaccination or from previous infections.

The present data from all over the world suggest that as the SARS-CoV-2 did not meet any resistance, could spread quickly across countries and caused havoc among local population. In India however, the virus met with stringent resistance by way of physical intervention & social distancing, which not only disallowed its spread far and wide but also broke its chain of movement locally. This abrupt slow down in the infective ability of the virus, has given India a unique opportunity to become the first place where herd protection against SARS-CoV-2 may be emerging. This conjecture is supported by gradual and steady increase in number of recovery from COVID-19 in India. Recovery in Indian States ranges between 40% - 90% compared to confirmed cases. Many such recovered patients showed presence of antibodies against the SARS-cov-2 and transfer of 'Plasma' taken from recovered patients were able to cure patients suffering from COVID-19. None of these patients have been reported so far to be re-infected with the virus suggesting memory immune cells may be protecting them from further infection.

A classical case of herd protection requires a significant percentage of people to be immune against the virus in a population. However, in case of Indian population the basic requirement for developing herd protection may have different parameters. That is because, in India a large number of people in the population have been immunized against many of the deadly virus borne diseases like TB, small pox etc either by vaccination in childhood or getting cured from the disease. Especially BCG was used for vaccinating a large number of individuals in Indian population. A clinical trial conducted in American-Indian and Alaska Native populations, Bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG) vaccine has shown to reduce the risk for developing lung cancer (4). In a mouse model of Lung cancer, we were able to generate a long term protective immune response by injecting FLT-3 ligand (FLT-3L) following irradiation in a lung cancer model (5). It may be an early development but things could be moving in that direction. Another factor, to be considered is the diverse nature of the Indian population with some states being affected more than the others. So it is reasonable to believe that some States could develop herd protection earlier than the other.

Another aspect to be considered seriously for the success for development of herd protection is though prolonged and sustained Lockdown has been by and large effective but social distancing norms have not been rigorously adhered to in the population. Along with such limitations and the recent difficulties in movement of huge number of migrant laborers without maintaining social distancing, to their home town across India may pose a hindrance in early herd protection during period of Lockdown. However, the

silver lining that such breakdown of social distancing should have resulted in much higher number of COVID-19 cases; until now that is not the case. Given the fact that such things did not happen, points to the fact in majority of Indian migrant laborers may have protection against the viral infection. Therefore, at this juncture to achieve the goal of herd protection earlier, more efforts must be directed to implement social distancing and sustain the ongoing Lockdown to bring the rate of COVID-19 cases to $\leq 1\%$.

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V. References:

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FIGURES

NUMBER OF COVID-19 CASES BETWEEN 15TH MARCH TO 16 MAY, 2020.

FIGURE-1

Figure 1: The graph depicts the total number of COVID-19 positive individuals in Indian Population at different time points between 15 March, 2020 and 17 May, 2020. As evident from the graph, there is an increase in number of positive cases in the population before and after three Lockdowns were implemented.

**PERCENT CHANGE IN COVID -19 CASES FOLLOWING
THREE LOCKDOWNS**

FIGURE-2

FIGURE 2: The graph shows the percent change in COVID-19 cases from 15 March, 2020 until 17 May, 2020. The graph reflects that following implementation of three 'Lockdowns' a flattened curve was maintained.

PERCENT CHANGE IN COVID-19 CASES FOLLOWING INTERVENTION

FIGURE-3

FIGURE 3: The figure shows the effect of three subsequent lockdowns on the percent of COVID-19 cases in the population. A comparative study the initial volatility was stabilised during the period of third lockdown and the percent increase in COVID-19 cases stabilised $\leq 5\%$.

TREND LINE OF PERCENT DIFFERENCE OF COVID-19 CASES DURING LOCKDOWN-I, II AND III

FIGURE 4

FIGURE-4: The graph shows a comparative correlation in COVID-19 cases during three lockdowns. The trend line shows that the initial volatility of lockdown-1 period was reduced during subsequent lockdown-2 and lockdown-3 periods respectively. The squared R value also increased.

FIGURE:5

FIGURE-5: The Figure shows number of discharged/recovered individuals on each day from 08 May 2020 to 17 May, 2020, compared to total number of COVID-19 cases.

FIGURE- 6: The Figure shows the percentage change in recovery of patients from COVID 19 cases. The trend line shows a positive correlation in recovery of patients from COVID-19.

IMPORTANCE OF EARLY LOCKDOWN ON FATALITY IN THE USA

Source: NY Times

FIGURE 7

FIGURE 7: The figure shows the positive effect of intervention on saving lives in the USA. It is clear that there was six times increase in fatalities for delayed implementation of social distancing.